

Synthesis, Structural and Optical Properties of Cu Doped ZnTe Thin Films

Uddhao N. Ingle¹, Milind S. Kale²

¹Department of Electronics, Smt. G.G. Khadse College, Muktainagar Dist. Jalgaon

²Department of Electronics, D.N.C.V.P.S. Shirish Madhukarrao Chaudhari College, Jalgaon

Corresponding Author: uddhaoingle@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

Cu doped ZnTe thin films were deposited onto glass substrates by using thermal evaporation technique. The structure analysis of the film was performed by XRD technique. The surface morphological analysis was carried out by using optical microscope. The optical band gap were calculated by UV-VIS spectrometry analysis. The XRD reveals that, the thin films are polycrystalline in nature. The crystal structure is found to be hexagonal shape. The microscopic images reveals that films are homogenous and particles are uniformly deposited on the substrate. Optical band gap, was calculated from the absorption spectra is situated in the range of 2 eV.

Keywords: Cu doped ZnTe Thin films, XRD, UV-VIS.

1. INTRODUCTION

The II-VI compound group semiconductor materials is an important semiconductor material because of its extensive potentials applications for the development of various modern technologies of solid-state devices like blue light emitting diodes, laser diodes, solar cells, microwave devices, etc. ZnTe is one of the interesting materials for potential photovoltaic applications in different opto-electronics devices such as photodiodes, solar cells, and LED [1-4]. The ZnTe can be used as a window material in solar cells. In addition, it reduces the toxic nature of CdS thin films in currently developed thin film solar cells [5].

A variety of methods have been developed for the preparation of Cu doped ZnTe thin films such as physical vapor deposition under vacuum, molecular beam epitaxy, CBD, Sillar, Chemical vapor deposition, Solution growth, spray pyrolysis, molecular beam epitaxy etc [2, 6, 7].

In this paper, structural, morphological and optical properties of Cu doped ZnTe thin film grown by thermal evaporation technique, are investigate.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

First of all, the Cu doped ZnTe powder were prepared by using $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, ZnCl_2 and Telluride (Te) metal powder by reflux method in chemical synthesis technique. After chemical synthesis process, filter the precipitate and washed the solid with distilled water and ethanol to remove byproducts and un-reacted materials. Finally, dry the powder under IR lamp for 2-3 hours. Then black or gray precipitate was formed which indicate the formation of ZnTe:Cu powder. Then the prepared powder compound of ZnTe:Cu was used for the deposition and were placed in a Mo boat by using Thermal Evaporation Technique.

The prepared powder compound of Cu doped ZnTe was used for the deposition.

During the deposition, the pressure was keep about 10^{-5} torr. The substrate to source distance was keeping about 13 cm. The samples of different thicknesses were deposit under similar conditions. The thickness of the films was monitored by quartz crystal digital thickness monitor (Model No. DTM-101), provided by Hind-Hi Vac. The deposition rate was maintained 5 - 10 Å/sec throughout sample preparation.

Before thermal evaporation, the glass substrates were clean thoroughly using detergent, chromic acid, isopropyl alcohol, pure distilled water and finally acetone.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. X-ray diffraction (XRD) Analysis:

To study the structural properties, the grown sample was characterized by XRD technique. The XRD patterns of grown Cu doped ZnTe thin film having thickness of 1000 Å is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: The XRD patterns of Cu doped ZnTe thin film.

The XRD patterns shows the samples is polycrystalline with orthorhombic crystal structure. The 2θ peak observed at 24.8° , 33.5° , 47.35° , 49.5° and 65° exhibit the formation of the hexagonal structure phase of Cu doped ZnTe which correspond to the (0 1 10), (1 4 11), (022), (202) and (041) planes of reflections. The presence of number of peaks indicates that the films are polycrystalline in nature. The values of lattice parameters are found $a = 5.379$, $b = 5.9471$ and $c = 5.01$. The crystal size was calculated by Scherrer equation.

$$\text{Crystallite size} = (0.94 \times \lambda) / (\beta \times \text{Cos } \Theta)$$

Where, λ = wavelength of incident X-Ray, β = Full width at half maxima in radian and Θ = Bragg angle/diffracted angle. The crystal size was found to be 346.60.

3.2. Morphological Analysis:

The surface morphological properties, the grown sample was observed under optical microscope. The figure 2 shows the optical microscopic image of grown Cu doped ZnTe thin film having thickness of 1000 Å.

Figure 2: Optical microscopic images of Cu doped ZnTe thin film.

From the micrograph images, it is observed that the film is uniform. The nano size grains were uniformly distributed over smooth homogeneous background and well cover on substrate. The sample is free from any microscopy defect like cracks or peeling. Similarly it is observed that the particles forms the cluster with random shape.

3.3. UV-VIS Analysis:

To study the optical properties were studied with UV-VIS spectrometry. The figure 3 shows the optical properties of grown Cu doped ZnTe thin film having thickness of 1000 Å.

The optical absorption spectra were obtain in 350 nm to 900 nm wavelength range by employing a Shimadzu 2450 UV-Visible model of the spectrophotometer. According to absorbance and transmittance it is found that the film has high absorbance. The optical band gap of these films has been calculated using the relation (Tauc 1974).

$$\alpha h\nu = A (h\nu - E_g)^n$$

where, $h\nu$ is the photon energy, α is the absorption coefficient, E_g the band gap, A is constant and, $n = 0.5$ for direct band gap material and $n = 2$ for indirect band gap material.

Figure 3: Optical properties of grown Cu doped ZnTe thin film

Figure 4: Band gap of grown Cu doped ZnTe Thin Film.

The plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus $h\nu$ for Cu doped ZnTe films is presented in Fig. 4. The straight line portion is extrapolated to cut the x-axis, which gives the energy gap. This figure clearly shows the the optical band gap is 2 eV [8], which is in good agreement for solar cell and other optical devices. Hence, the Cu doped ZnTe, can be used in development of efficient photovoltaic application.

Conclusions

The study of Cu doped ZnTe thin films deposited by vacuum thermal evaporation technique revealed the sample is a polycrystalline structure. The grown sample is homogenous and free from any defects. The optical band gap is 2 eV allowing it to efficiently capture high-energy. Materials with this band gap has enhanced stability and

high-performance, due to which is in good agreement for solar cell manufacturing.

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